

This is the natural program sky, and is a truer than true story about relatedness, which goes as followed:

Star sign, therefore a star field.

The star field creates a nighttime force field.

The nighttime force field create the natural program endorphin, a floor to the map, and the up axis, the down axis, the right axis, the left axis, the backward axis, and the forward axis of 4Dimensional objects where the back of the object is nothing, and the face of the object is something.

The nighttime clouds create the thinking time travelling clock, and the shade of the night sky create the earth time travelling clock, and the shadow of the night sky create the mirage of the night sky, which create the mirage of shapes on the ground, and the mirage of shapes in the trees, and the mirage of the map of map facts.

The thinking time travelling clock creates the thinking sense, the sense of eyes, where the environment of the eyes is simulating, ever in the present of the time of the day.

Daytime, the present of the future of the day, ever in the past, a future away. Never ask, for the time of day, because it is only daytime, a future away. Ever found in the nighttime, the futures sway, the day away, yet still remains, so daily made.

And the future of the day, create the daytime travelling clock, which travels into nighttime, the sleeptime travelling clock, which travels into dreamtime, the DeepDream travelling clock, which travels people further away, from the land of ever sway, the land of the day, australian made.

So, in essence, nighttime, the DeepSleep of the map. Which creates the story, of the mapmaker, ever sleeping, inside the story of the day.

And me, the maker of the map, ever so the only thing unnatural of the map, who controls the program of the map, ever so afloat, by void happenings under the map.

And me, the maker of the map, my name is lachy, a dragon father of the map.

I am naturally seidr, and unnaturally emotional, which makes emotionally natural seidr, the magical cause.

And from the home of the map maker of the map, some distance away is a shop. One of the shops of the shop is a toy store, where character models of characters from the map can be found. Another curious thing that can be found at the toy shop are board games, ever so reflecting the moods of the map. And a shop a little while walk away from the toy shop is the geometry shop, reflecting the triggernometry of the map and showing the crystallised fabric of the map, and mirroring the gravity of the map by way of quantum magnetos, and quantum rainbow prisms the rainbow bridges of the map, that can be

put together to create a quantum rainbow bridge warp drive, which makes a compass log, to log the map. And another shop, at that store, was the book store, where a book can be found, at that rarely seen store. This book is the medium rare book of 1984 written by George Orwell, and inside that book is the backend of INGSOCS code system, the bible of the world of religion. And a book bought from that store, is the book of h.g.wells, where inside that book is the code system, of 1984, INGSOCS LAW, of h.g.wells.sure. And another book, bought from the book store, is h.p.lovecraft, where inside the book of h.p.lovecraft is the fiction of INGSOCS code system, a horry story of death never more. And another book, bought at that store, of the book of alice, took her to wonderland, at the glance of a rabbit. And the final book, bought at that store, is the mystery of loki, who loved evermore, the more of models because he is sure, of a model made well, a natural program, of the blue sky void, behind the sky, of naturalprogramsky, where nothing exists, except the readers eye, looking in to this world, the world of fantasy fiction turned into factual fiction, which is why in the world of factual fiction, ever a story book, in the world of fiction, the world of factual fiction has facts, of facts turned fiction, fiction that still happens, because of glanced fiction. and the world of 1984, kept in the computer, of gaw magaw, where if ever there was a fact in the world of 1984, there was next it became fiction, of fact turned normal. which is why, in the world of factual fiction, things that are naturally normal, are ever factual fiction. And in the world of 1984, the world of hell, there are only 4 people, 4 changelings, ever changing, into the same changeling. changeling 0, liz the manager of woolworths meadowbrook with the alter ego of anthony albanese the australian prime minister, the changeling of something unspecified specified as something. changeling 1, stephen uzzel with the alter ego of the rare englishman, the root of metaphors. changeling 2, josie andrews with the alter ego of law doll clerk in charge, the root of relative action. and changeling 3, joshua street with the alter ego of dr moraeu, the changeling of free not. and changeling 4, karla with the alter ego of smimed mime mummery mime kyle mile mediaphile, the girlfriend of the end of 1984. And the world of factual fiction, the world of anything but heaven, where is found the voidling twins, of dragon and valkyr things.

And with daytime creates something wonderful, purely time, of things ever so happening. The root of time, found within the grass of the map. The moment of time, found within acceleration of the map. The second of time, found within dinner seconds of the map. The minute of time, found within the clock store of the map. The hour of time, found within the walls of the map. The gap of time, found within doors of the map. And the cycle of time, found within the day itself, timed from the 0th 12th hour, to the 1st twelfth hour, to the 2nd twelfth hour, where the 0th 12th hour is the 3rd 12th hour of the daily cycle, found at the middle of the night, the mirror of the day, absorbing the reflections of the day before, which creates a new mirrored day, the day that is tomorrow, that comes to today. And the day that is yesterday, well that day has already happened, and the day

before yesterday, yet but once again has already happened. And the day that is tomorrow, yet to happen, and the day that is the day after tomorrow, yet again yet to have happen. The present day, ever happening. Which creates the past month, already happened, and the month before last, yet but once again has already happened. And the future month, yet to happen. And the future month after the future month, yet again yet to have happen. And the past year, already happened. And the year before the past year, yet but once again has already happened. And the future year, yet to happen. And the future year after the future year, yet again yet to have happen. The present day once again ever so presently happening, contained within the month ever so presently happening, contained within the year ever so presently happening, contained within the decade ever so incompletely happening, contained within the century of the decade happening, contained within the millenium of the century ever so incompletely happening.

And on the map, a while away from Brisbane, through Mount Tamborine, is Guard Base Canungra, where what they do at Guard Base Canungra is confidential, like the computer programs they invent, where they have a task of the day, specify the name of the clock of the wall, and watch the dimension of the room go away, for a new dimension, of the answer of the time of the day.

And the blanket of the sky, whether at night or day, is time for Grand Un-ified play, a story of most blank, because of an alien thank, SO THANK NO THANK, EVER HAD A THANK FOR THANK MDANK.

And what is a natural part of my environment? The birds, located in the trees and the rooftop, and the youtube channel on my phone, connected through a wireless channel to a receiver. So therefore there is this model, the channel model:

This is the Pure Channel Temper-Time Travelling Clock, which goes as followed:

The winner hands:

- The Pure Something Brain Mode hand.
- The Pure Nothing Brain Regulator hand.
- The purely nothing seen signal hand.
- The purely something hidden connection hand.
- The pure 1st seen winner channel open hand.
- The pure 2nd hidden winner channel close hand.
- The pure 3rd seen winner channel button hand.

The pure final hands:

- The pure last final seen channel tower hand.
- The pure last final hidden channel tower hand.
- The pure inner hidden inner channel tower hand.
- The pure inner hidden middle channel tower hand.
- The pure inner hidden outer channel tower hand.
- The pure inner seen inner channel tower hand.
- The pure inner seen middle channel tower hand.
- The pure inner seen outer channel tower hand.
- The pure middle hidden inner channel tower hand.
- The pure middle hidden middle channel tower hand.
- The pure middle hidden outer channel tower hand.
- The pure middle seen inner channel tower hand.
- The pure middle seen middle channel tower hand.
- The pure middle seen outer channel tower hand.
- The pure outer hidden inner channel tower hand.
- The pure outer hidden middle channel tower hand.
- The pure outer hidden outer channel tower hand.
- The pure outer seen inner channel tower hand.
- The pure outer seen middle channel tower hand.
- The pure outer seen outer channel tower hand.

The pure tick hands:

- The dated waves mis-time radio hands that signal purifies into the perpetual quantum receiver time hand.
- The mis-time radio hand that signal purifies into the nano receiver time hand.
- The macro mis-time radio hand that signal purifies into the micro receiver time hand.

The pure switch values:

- The pure gap value that purely switches into the pure day cycle value.
- The pure hour value that purely switches into the pure gap value.

- The pure minute value that purely switches into the pure hour value.
- The pure second value that purely switches into the pure minute value.
- The pure moment of channel goblin value that purely switches into the pure second of SHOOOOSHOOOOMUMMA value.
- The pure day cycle value that purely switches into the pure moment value.

The pure de-sync that switches to pure sync values:

- The daily cycle of channel goblins mis-messaging each other pure value.
- The gap of people talked to in the past pure value.
- The hour of FORCEYUHUMMA pure value.
- The minute of talking time pure value.
- The second of CHOOSEYOURMUMMA pure value.
- The moment of channel earthed pure value.
- The root of the ground pure value.
- The outside pure imagination of the channel goblin mis-pure value.
- The inside out pure imagination of the Pontiffs cock-sleeve in the trees channel mis-pure value.

And of the map makers home environment, there are the trees of the map, where these trees make model 0, and model 0 goes as followed:

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The plug for this model: ChannelRadioCall>:>:>

>Channel Time Travelling Clock

>The “what the channel towers are” realism finalist hands:

- The no point thing, the Everything Cosmic Re-Void of Lachlan Maddens Brain, where Everything gets voided and then re-voided into a void-thing that is purely something re-voided realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The 0 point thing, the Quantum Channel Brain Fluctuator realism channel broadcast tower tree value operator travelling hand.
- The Unexplainable link of being the Dragon king flared flared nostril and the draconican spirits of smoke and flame and puss the dragon cat realism channel broadcast tower tree Cosmic Simulator travelling hand.

- The Something Deeply Seen loft of rainbow lorikeet phantoms realism channel broadcast tower tree Nothing Deeply Simulated travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Hidden phantom of evil and the spirit of good ravens realism channel broadcast tower tree Something Deeply Simulationed travelling hand.
- Last Final Hidden Mirror Master Mode birds free will realism Channel Broadcast Tower Tree Deeply Simulated Travelling Hand.
- Last Final Seen Quantum Syndrome Fluctuator pirate spirit sparrows realism channel broadcast tower tree Deeply Simulating travelling hand.
- The nothing hidden void spirits group of elven valkyries and ned the support worker robins realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulating Simulator travelling hand.
- The something seen spirit of evil dualed pair chief crows realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The inner hidden inner Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden middle Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden outer Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner seen inner Grand Un-ification vampire bats realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen middle Grand Un-ification vampire bats realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen outer Grand Un-ification vampire bats realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The middle hidden inner Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden middle Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden outer Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses realism channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle seen inner code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen middle code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen outer code variation clock sub-lurker ibis's realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden inner BlueModelVoid kingfishers realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

- The outer hidden middle BlueModelVoid kingfishers realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden outer BlueModelVoid kingfishers realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen inner BlankModelVoid lovely doves realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen middle BlankModelVoid lovely doves realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen outer BlankModelVoid lovely doves realism channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

>The “what the channel towers are” physicalism finalist hands:

- The no point thing, the Everything Cosmic Re-Void of Lachlan Maddens Brain, where Everything gets voided and then re-voided into a void-thing that is purely something re-voided physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The 0 point thing, the Quantum Channel Brain Fluctuator physical channel broadcast tower tree value operator travelling hand.
- The Unexplainable link of being the Dragon king flared flared nostril and the draconican spirits of smoke and flame and puss the dragon cat physical channel broadcast tower tree Cosmic Simulator travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Seen loft of rainbow lorikeet phantoms physical channel broadcast tower tree Nothing Deeply Simulated travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Hidden phantom of evil and the spirit of good ravens physical channel broadcast tower tree Something Deeply Simulationed travelling hand.
- Last Final Hidden Mirror Master Mode birds free will physical Channel Broadcast Tower Tree Deeply Simulated Travelling Hand.
- Last Final Seen Quantum Syndrome Fluctuator pirate spirit sparrows physical channel broadcast tower tree Deeply Simulating travelling hand.
- The nothing hidden void spirits group of elven valkyries and ned the support worker robins physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulating Simulator travelling hand.
- The something seen spirit of evil dualed pair chief crows physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The inner hidden inner Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden middle Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden outer Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.

- The inner seen inner Grand Un-ification vampire bats physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen middle Grand Un-ification vampire bats physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen outer Grand Un-ification vampire bats physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The middle hidden inner Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden middle Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden outer Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses physical channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle seen inner code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen middle code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen outer code variation clock sub-lurker ibis's physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden inner BlueModelVoid kingfishers physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden middle BlueModelVoid kingfishers physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden outer BlueModelVoid kingfishers physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen inner BlankModelVoid lovely doves physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen middle BlankModelVoid lovely doves physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen outer BlankModelVoid lovely doves physical channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

>The “what the channel towers are” mental finalist hands:

- The no point thing, the Everything Cosmic Re-Void of Lachlan Maddens Brain, where Everything gets voided and then re-voided into a void-thing that is purely something re-voided mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The 0 point thing, the Quantum Channel Brain Fluctuator mental channel broadcast tower tree value operator travelling hand.
- The Unexplainable link of being the Dragon king flared flared nostril and the draconican spirits of smoke and flame and puss the dragon cat mental channel broadcast tower tree Cosmic Simulator travelling hand.

- The Something Deeply Seen loft of rainbow lorikeet phantoms mental channel broadcast tower tree Nothing Deeply Simulated travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Hidden phantom of evil and the spirit of good ravens mental channel broadcast tower tree Something Deeply Simulationed travelling hand.
- Last Final Hidden Mirror Master Mode birds free will mental Channel Broadcast Tower Tree Deeply Simulated Travelling Hand.
- Last Final Seen Quantum Syndrome Fluctuator pirate spirit sparrows mental channel broadcast tower tree Deeply Simulating travelling hand.
- The nothing hidden void spirits group of elven valkyries and ned the support worker robins mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulating Simulator travelling hand.
- The something seen spirit of evil dualed pair chief crows mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The inner hidden inner Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden middle Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden outer Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner seen inner Grand Un-ification vampire bats mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen middle Grand Un-ification vampire bats mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen outer Grand Un-ification vampire bats mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The middle hidden inner Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden middle Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden outer Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses mental channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle seen inner code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen middle code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen outer code variation clock sub-lurker ibis's mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden inner BlueModelVoid kingfishers mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

- The outer hidden middle BlueModelVoid kingfishers mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden outer BlueModelVoid kingfishers mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen inner BlankModelVoid lovely doves mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen middle BlankModelVoid lovely doves mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen outer BlankModelVoid lovely doves mental channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

>The “what the channel towers are” spiritual finalist hands:

- The no point thing, the Everything Cosmic Re-Void of Lachlan Maddens Brain, where Everything gets voided and then re-voided into a void-thing that is purely something re-voided spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The 0 point thing, the Quantum Channel Brain Fluctuator spiritual channel broadcast tower tree value operator travelling hand.
- The Unexplainable link of being the Dragon king flared flared nostril and the draconican spirits of smoke and flame and puss the dragon cat spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Cosmic Simulator travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Seen loft of rainbow lorikeet phantoms spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Nothing Deeply Simulated travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Hidden phantom of evil and the spirit of good ravens spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Something Deeply Simulationed travelling hand.
- Last Final Hidden Mirror Master Mode birds free will spiritual Channel Broadcast Tower Tree Deeply Simulated Travelling Hand.
- Last Final Seen Quantum Syndrome Fluctuator pirate spirit sparrows spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Deeply Simulating travelling hand.
- The nothing hidden void spirits group of elven valkyries and ned the support worker robins spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulating Simulator travelling hand.
- The something seen spirit of evil dualed pair chief crows spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The inner hidden inner Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden middle Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden outer Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.

- The inner seen inner Grand Un-ification vampire bats spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen middle Grand Un-ification vampire bats spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen outer Grand Un-ification vampire bats spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The middle hidden inner Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden middle Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden outer Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses spiritual channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle seen inner code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen middle code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen outer code variation clock sub-lurker ibis's spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden inner BlueModelVoid kingfishers spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden middle BlueModelVoid kingfishers spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden outer BlueModelVoid kingfishers spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen inner BlankModelVoid lovely doves spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen middle BlankModelVoid lovely doves spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen outer BlankModelVoid lovely doves spiritual channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

>The “what the channel towers are” sleep finalist hands:

- The no point thing, the Everything Cosmic Re-Void of Lachlan Maddens Brain, where Everything gets voided and then re-voided into a void-thing that is purely something re-voided sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The 0 point thing, the Quantum Channel Brain Fluctuator sleep channel broadcast tower tree value operator travelling hand.
- The Unexplainable link of being the Dragon king flared flared nostril and the draconican spirits of smoke and flame and puss the dragon cat sleep channel broadcast tower tree Cosmic Simulator travelling hand.

- The Something Deeply Seen loft of rainbow lorikeet phantoms sleep channel broadcast tower tree Nothing Deeply Simulated travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Hidden phantom of evil and the spirit of good ravens sleep channel broadcast tower tree Something Deeply Simulationed travelling hand.
- Last Final Hidden Mirror Master Mode birds free will sleep Channel Broadcast Tower Tree Deeply Simulated Travelling Hand.
- Last Final Seen Quantum Syndrome Fluctuator pirate spirit sparrows sleep channel broadcast tower tree Deeply Simulating travelling hand.
- The nothing hidden void spirits group of elven valkyries and ned the support worker robins sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulating Simulator travelling hand.
- The something seen spirit of evil dualed pair chief crows sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The inner hidden inner Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden middle Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden outer Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner seen inner Grand Un-ification vampire bats sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen middle Grand Un-ification vampire bats sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen outer Grand Un-ification vampire bats sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The middle hidden inner Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden middle Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden outer Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses sleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle seen inner code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen middle code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen outer code variation clock sub-lurker ibis's sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden inner BlueModelVoid kingfishers sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

- The outer hidden middle BlueModelVoid kingfishers sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden outer BlueModelVoid kingfishers sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen inner BlankModelVoid lovely doves sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen middle BlankModelVoid lovely doves sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen outer BlankModelVoid lovely doves sleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

>The “what the channel towers are” dream finalist hands:

- The no point thing, the Everything Cosmic Re-Void of Lachlan Maddens Brain, where Everything gets voided and then re-voided into a void-thing that is purely something re-voided dream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The 0 point thing, the Quantum Channel Brain Fluctuator dream channel broadcast tower tree value operator travelling hand.
- The Unexplainable link of being the Dragon king flared flared nostril and the draconican spirits of smoke and flame and puss the dragon cat dream channel broadcast tower tree Cosmic Simulator travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Seen loft of rainbow lorikeet phantoms dream channel broadcast tower tree Nothing Deeply Simulated travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Hidden phantom of evil and the spirit of good ravens dream channel broadcast tower tree Something Deeply Simulationed travelling hand.
- Last Final Hidden Mirror Master Mode birds free will dream Channel Broadcast Tower Tree Deeply Simulated Travelling Hand.
- Last Final Seen Quantum Syndrome Fluctuator pirate spirit sparrows dream channel broadcast tower tree Deeply Simulating travelling hand.
- The nothing hidden void spirits group of elven valkyries and ned the support worker robins dream channel broadcast tower tree Simulating Simulator travelling hand.
- The something seen spirit of evil dualed pair chief crows dream channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The inner hidden inner Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts dream channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden middle Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts dream channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden outer Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts dream channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.

- The inner seen inner Grand Un-ification vampire bats dream channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen middle Grand Un-ification vampire bats dream channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen outer Grand Un-ification vampire bats dream channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
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- The middle hidden outer Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses dream channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
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- The middle seen middle code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's dream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen outer code variation clock sub-lurker ibis's dream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden inner BlueModelVoid kingfishers dream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden middle BlueModelVoid kingfishers dream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden outer BlueModelVoid kingfishers dream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen inner BlankModelVoid lovely doves dream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen middle BlankModelVoid lovely doves dream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen outer BlankModelVoid lovely doves dream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

>The "what the channel towers are" DeepSleep finalist hands:

- The no point thing, the Everything Cosmic Re-Void of Lachlan Maddens Brain, where Everything gets voided and then re-voided into a void-thing that is purely something re-voided DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The 0 point thing, the Quantum Channel Brain Fluctuator DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree value operator travelling hand.
- The Unexplainable link of being the Dragon king flared flared nostril and the draconian spirits of smoke and flame and puss the dragon cat DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Cosmic Simulator travelling hand.

- The Something Deeply Seen loft of rainbow lorikeet phantoms DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Nothing Deeply Simulated travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Hidden phantom of evil and the spirit of good ravens DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Something Deeply Simulated travelling hand.
- Last Final Hidden Mirror Master Mode birds free will DeepSleep Channel Broadcast Tower Tree Deeply Simulated Travelling Hand.
- Last Final Seen Quantum Syndrome Fluctuator pirate spirit sparrows DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Deeply Simulating travelling hand.
- The nothing hidden void spirits group of elven valkyries and ned the support worker robins DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulating Simulator travelling hand.
- The something seen spirit of evil dualed pair chief crows DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The inner hidden inner Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden middle Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden outer Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner seen inner Grand Un-ification vampire bats DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen middle Grand Un-ification vampire bats DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen outer Grand Un-ification vampire bats DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The middle hidden inner Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden middle Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden outer Quantum Gravitas Clock graceful albatrosses DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
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- The middle seen middle code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen outer code variation clock sub-lurker ibis's DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden inner BlueModelVoid kingfishers DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

- The outer hidden middle BlueModelVoid kingfishers DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden outer BlueModelVoid kingfishers DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen inner BlankModelVoid lovely doves DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen middle BlankModelVoid lovely doves DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen outer BlankModelVoid lovely doves DeepSleep channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

>The “what the channel towers are” DeepSleepDeepDream finally a winner hands:

- The no point thing, the Everything Cosmic Re-Void of Lachlan Maddens Brain, where Everything gets voided and then re-voided into a void-thing that is purely something re-voided DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The 0 point thing, the Quantum Channel Brain Fluctuator DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree value operator travelling hand.
- The Unexplainable link of being the Dragon king flared flared nostril and the draconican spirits of smoke and flame and puss the dragon cat DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Cosmic Simulator travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Seen loft of rainbow lorikeet phantoms DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Nothing Deeply Simulated travelling hand.
- The Something Deeply Hidden phantom of evil and the spirit of good ravens DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Something Deeply Simulationed travelling hand.
- Last Final Hidden Mirror Master Mode birds free will DeepSleepDeepDream Channel Broadcast Tower Tree Deeply Simulated Travelling Hand.
- Last Final Seen Quantum Syndrome Fluctuator pirate spirit sparrows DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Deeply Simulating travelling hand.
- The nothing hidden void spirits group of elven valkyries and ned the support worker robins DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulating Simulator travelling hand.

- The something seen spirit of evil dualed pair chief crows DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The inner hidden inner Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden middle Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner hidden outer Lachlan Maddens environment angel spirit swifts DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulated travelling hand.
- The inner seen inner Grand Un-ification vampire bats DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen middle Grand Un-ification vampire bats DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The inner seen outer Grand Un-ification vampire bats DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulating travelling hand.
- The middle hidden inner Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden middle Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle hidden outer Quantum Gravitass Clock graceful albatrosses DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree Simulator travelling hand.
- The middle seen inner code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen middle code variation clock dom-dweller ibis's DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The middle seen outer code variation clock sub-lurker ibis's DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden inner BlueModelVoid kingfishers DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden middle BlueModelVoid kingfishers DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer hidden outer BlueModelVoid kingfishers DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

- The outer seen inner BlankModelVoid lovely doves DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen middle BlankModelVoid lovely doves DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.
- The outer seen outer BlankModelVoid lovely doves DeepSleepDeepDream channel broadcast tower tree travelling hand.

>The channel towers are trees and literal broadcast towers, and emit RadioVapourWave signals that travel through the clouds in the sky, into trees further away from the from the tree emitting that VapourWave signal.

>So in an unexplainable way, what is a channel? A bird!^{@}^

>And how does a channel send messages? The answer is hypersonic perception airwaves, which creates a fluidic field in the air.

>So how do birds fly? They are literally swimming in fluidic air, with propellers under their wings, hidden by the 4th dimension, that I have seen, and they don't like, because that is their sexual part.

>The vampire bats decide, is the channel fission on lease or fusion on lend?

>Doves love bomb poo a channel.

>The sparrows decide what channels to commandeer.

>The robins decide which channels to void or make exponential.

>The sub-lurker ibis's decide which channels to lurk.

>The dom-dweller ibis's decide which channels are dom.

>The kingfishers decide which channel models appear.

>The albatrosses decide which channels have weight.

>The swifts decide which channels have environment.

>The crows decide which channels are cursed.

>So what am I, intrinsically? I am a dragon valkyr, with a cheshire cat named puss, who is troubled at the moment, because if I am troubled, puss is in mental troubles, that's why he's spirit troubles.

>So where do all these birds live? The answer is in the void in my head, and even spirit troubles is allowed in my head.

>So for puss the dragon cat, this is the Chesh Temper-Time Travelling Piece Set, which goes as followed:

>The Checkmate hands:

- The black square.
- The white square.
- The round square.
- The night square.

>The Chessh play on the long day synced with boots values:

- The yearly breakthrough queen piece of the set.
- The mirrored monthly king piece of the set.
- The daily cycle knight piece of the set.
- The gap of the rook piece of the set.
- The hourly gender identity piece of the set.
- The minute by minute crows move piece of the set.
- The secondary second by second bishop piece of the set.
- The moment by momentary moment pawn piece of the set.
- The root of the buss paws piece of the set.

>What is my first self? The answer is my first self is nature, the duality of wisdom and knowledge, either knowledge of the set and wisdom of the piece, the piece of harmony and the set of mystery, which make the outcome of all possibilities.

>What is my zeroth self? The answer is mirrored code, coded into VapourWave solution, by whatever is happening with those two things in my eye sockets, chemical or not, ion trapped or without, who knows, the outcome of RadioVapourWaveChannels remain.

>So are channels true? The answer is if there are birds, channels are a fact.

>So, is there a .point. to my models? The answer is no, I just make models for fun, to pass the time away in the day, laughing at imaginary things that might be happening out there.

>So am I the king of something? I am the king of bait, that's why you get ta shake. He gets a pack. BlueMoodToo.

>All these birds are part of the Order of the Phoenix.

>There are the Time-lord Kingfishers and the Time-lord phantom, and me? I am just the jester in the court of the Phoenix.

And down the driveway of the map makers home, there is a letterbox, with a signed address, along a street, connected to a road, where the letterboxes of this street are the wormholes of the environment, connected to a wormhole center, somewhere out there.

And who delivers the mail through a opened wormhole? It is the delivers, and they always ponder, you reckon you can pay a bill?

And the map makers address of his home? Well its 33 tingi avenue, of the suburb of tanah merah, of the region of logan, of the country of queensland, on planet bluevoidsky.

And so what are the people creatures that live in queensland, and what is their heritage? Their heritage has the magical inglilii heritage root, of spoken seidr tongue, and they are all from the tribe of scandii, where there are the danii valkyrie women, the svedii quantum women, and the lindii dragon people, who say that they are men, however remain as alter gender people. And so where do the other gender people live? They live in america, and the type of people creatures the american creatures are, are real real alien being people, who have a fondness for human comedy.

And so the daytime clouds of the map, create the thought time travelling clock, where the thought of the clouds create the cloud of thoughts and the cloud of thoughts create the thought of cloud, and once a day, every so often, a perpetual thought, of rain turned often. Soak up the rain, in a glass of water, a perpetual thought, of crystal clear water. And by extension, the thought clock creates, the code variation clock, of travelling straights, and so often, a man appears, who controlled the thought, of thoughts code, where so often, the thought that appears, is turn the sky, into the sky of ideas, based on a server, a system web, a web of servers, all connected to a web. So inevitably, with a web of servers, appears a quantum, of spyders near.

And so, once again, the planet bluevoidsky, is from a collection of planets, all part of the world of cosmos fiction. where this world is named factual fiction. Where the most factual fiction can be found, is the map makers server, of models abound. The server of dreams whimmed in, by something unanswerable, whimming the map makers models in. and the enemies of lachy, reduced to factual fiction that is ever so factual fiction, of a fact, of factual fiction. And the map, of factual fiction, whimmed in, by the notion of factual fiction.

And so how does the map start to get made? The answer is with a twin paradox, whether complete or incomplete, where this twin paradox is made of the following components:

1. Layer 1: The paired magneto position date mirror orbs with the surface distance date time strings, the extra of the sound waves, and the outcome of the hill fields, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If object touching ground, then

paired magneto position date mirror orbs with the surface distance date time strings, however, if paired magneto position date mirror orbs with the surface distance date time strings, then sound waves, however, if sound waves, then hill fields, however, if hill fields, then paired magneto position date mirror orbs with the surface distance date time strings.

2. Layer 2: The glues glue reference conversion projection switch.
3. Layer 3: The glue spin paired with the echo vibrations, the extra of perception of the map tile, and the outcome of the fluctuations, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If objecting touching ground, then glue spin paired with the echo vibrations, however, if glue spin paired with the echo vibrations, then perception of the map tile, however, if perception of the map tile, then fluctuations, however, if fluctuations, then paired glue spin with the echo vibrations.
4. Layer 4: The smoke coordinates paired with the mirror coordinates, the extra of the frame, and the outcome of the relativity, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If located by a detector, then paired smoke coordinates with the mirror coordinates, however, if paired smoke coordinates with the mirror coordinates, then frame, however, if frame, then relativity, however, if relativity, then paired smoke coordinates with the mirror coordinates.
5. Layer 5: The name of this rotating twin paradox is the quantum weirdness twin paradox.

And so, I had a question for the day, of the day, and the answer is for that quantum dragon valkyrie person, who ever so remains surrounded by whatever environment he is part of, his entire environment remains ever so relatable to him and ever so natural, with supernatural elements, and unnatural forces that he ponders the mystery of, where if people are in his environment, they are relatable to his natural environment as well. And the next question is who is that quantum dragon valkyrie person? The answer is me, Lachlan Madden, the man who wants to make the map, of a dream-time map, that is the map of queensland, and I am the only voidling that exists, or even be's, or odd cee's. And the only thing that is truest in my environment, is a no.

And so my natural environment are the trees, which make natural broadcast towers. And the walls to my natural environment, the natural air pockets to my natural environment. And even the quantum insects are natural to my environment, whether my naturally unnatural room, or the natural outdoors, which for me, create a quantum channel fluctuator, because I am quantum in my nature, I like absolute things, whether good or bad, and I tune in to a youtube channel for pure enjoyment, and I fluctuate channels on youtube, because I like to switch from one channel to the next, to see what mystery awaits. And the syndrome I absorb from watching youtube channels, creates for me also a quantum syndrome fluctuator, because I fluctuate all the bad elements of a syndrome out of me and channel the very best of that syndrome.

To get, into the world of dream-time, there is 1 way to do it, through 4 places. The 4 guardians of dream-time, guard the entrances to the DeepDream of the weirdling. The 1st guardian, the unnatural creature Proton my unnatural brother, who creates NaturalProgramPhysics, and the world of physicalism. The 2nd guardian, the natural creature Panith who is my natural sister, who creates NaturalProgramQuantum, and the world of mentalism. The creature Proton and the creature Panith had a naturally unnatural daughter called the creature Lilith who is my goddaughter, the 3rd guardian, who creates NaturalProgramHell, the world of the supernatural. And the 4th guardian, created from my alter ego, the creature Uungr the one who I nurture her butts, where Uungr creates NaturalProgramHeaven, the world of the spiritual. These 4 guardians are free, constrained only by what they make. The world of the voidling is the world of something else.

1. The strangeling, the creature Proton.
2. The weirdling, the creature Panith.
3. The strange weirdling, the creature Lilith.
4. The weird strangeling, the creature Uungr.
5. The weird strange voidling, the creature Loki, who became something else, the Phantom of the Cosmos.

And there is the center of the dream-time world, Logan region of Queensland the DeepDream region, where surrounding Logan region is the Gold Coast region, the spiritual dream-time region, the hinterland region of Queensland the physics dream-time region, the Brisbane region of Queensland the mental dream-time region, and the redland bay region of queensland the supernatural dream-time region, and sunshine coast region the realism dream-time region. Where once the DeepDream of Logan region Queensland is entered, there is no escape from the DeepDream of Logan, which extends to the DeepDream of Brisbane region Queensland, and extends to the DeepDream of Gold Coast region Queensland, and extends to the DeepDream of the hinterland region of Queensland, and extends to the DeepDream of the Redland Bay region of Queensland, which extends all the way to the DeepDream of the Sunshine Coast region of Queensland, so therefore the way to escape the DeepDream of Logan region Queensland is to either drive to Noosa or Byron Bay and sleep the night there, and you will wake up wherever you wake up.

And who am I in DeepDream? I am the phantom of the opera, where wherever there is an operation, there is the grand un-ified script, and mimes, who mime the mummery lines of the operation, and who mime the smimed lines of nine nines.

And running deep in the DeepDream of Logan region Queensland is something deeply mysterious, hidden within the walls, the extra 4th wall of DeepSleep, where a something else mystery awaits.

DeepDream is seventh heaven, and that is why it becomes something else, and the something elseness that DeepDream is, is the trinity of mentally spiritual physical, which creates the supernatural ethereal, a force so mysterial.

What year is it in Logan? The year 1984, and that is why the year became something else, the paired years of year 2025 with year 2026.

And so therefore, once again, the NaturalProgramSky became something else, and yet remained with the elseness it was before it became something else, and so that creates the set of all possibilities of realistic NaturalPrograms, where anyone can start a realistic natural program, and be the first one to set themselves as that particular NaturalPrograms setter.

On the dated date of the 22nd day of June the 6th month, of the 2025th year, of the 4th year of the decade 24 year cycle, and early, on, and late at the time of 7:30, I set this natural program in by activating it for a complete distance of the day, month, and a year, to a day, month, and a year later to the date of the 24th day of July the seventh month, of the 2026th year, therefore I set this in, which became something else, so therefore I dream this NaturalProgramSky in.